

THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN IMPROVING THE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article examines the role of emotional intelligence in improving the qualifications of future teachers and also provides valuable information about the formation of interpersonal competence of teachers, further improvement of their emotional intelligence, and timely completion of assignments and tasks in the specialty. It should be noted that the issue of emotional intelligence in psychology is a controversial topic. According to many scientists opinion, emotional intelligence is the key to success in professional activities, communication skills, and useful work.

Key words: emotional intelligence, emotional, contention, intelligence, potential, professional activity, competence, teacher

In the world's educational and research institutions, research is being conducted to improve the psychological competence of future teachers by conducting psychodiagnostics of emotional intelligence, human intelligence and its connection with the social environment, studying the influence of intelligence on human activity, and improving the psychological conditions that serve the development of emotional intelligence. In this regard, it is necessary to develop the competencies of future teachers in interpersonal relationships, further improve their emotional intelligence, complete assignments, and on-site assignments promptly, and be able to quickly overcome situations in unpleasant and difficult situations. situations, as well as explore the characteristics that determine the development of emotional intelligence in a leadership mood. It should be said that the issue of emotional intelligence in psychology is considered a controversial topic. According to many scientists opinion, emotional intelligence is the key to success in professional activities, communication skills, and useful work. A person's emotional intelligence is also related to emotional leadership. A well-developed person knows how to convey his feelings to other people. This will create an atmosphere of trust and cooperation in the team. Therefore, although the study of emotional intelligence is becoming increasingly popular in science, the phenomenological aspect of this psychological trait remains unclear in research. Bipocally, the problem of substantiating emotional intelligence attracts the attention of many young psychologists. Therefore, studying the nature of related psychological research, analyzing its uniqueness, and detailing the most advanced approach and conceptual framework are becoming increasingly essential tasks.

In the field of hospice research, there are many approaches to explaining the concept of emotional intelligence. To this approach J. Mape, P. Nightingale, D. Goleman, P. Ban-On, P. Pobepts, J. Matthews, M. Zeidnep, N. A prime example of this is the teaching of emotional intelligence and the model of emotional intelligence developed by Zallap. According to this model, emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to recognize one's own emotions and the emotions of others.

In social psychology, there is a specific scientific school in the field of emotional intelligence research, within which a new conceptual framework for the study of emotional intelligence can be developed. From a scientific point of view, researchers have paid much attention to the phenomenological, ontogenetic, structural and functional aspects of the problem of emotional intelligence. Below we will analyze the researcher's opinion regarding the study of emotional intelligence in psychological research. M.A. According to Alfepova, the basis of the inventive structure of emotional intelligence is the following group of abilities:

- ability to express your feelings;
- the ability to rationally manage your emotions;
- the ability to assess the emotional state of others and self-motivation, etc.

The disadvantage of this approach is that the author confuses emotional intelligence with general intelligence. That is, the author paid a lot of attention to cognitive activity. The G.G. Gorskova in his research P. supports the idea proposed by Solovey. He defines emotional intelligence as the ability to understand emotional reactions and analyze intellectually.

Typically, the most important part of a person's emotional intelligence is the subject's understanding of his or her emotions. The end product of emotional intelligence is the ability to make a decision based on a differentiated assessment of an event that has personal significance, reflects emotion, and interprets the situation. Thus, emotional intelligence provides people with a wide variety of ways to achieve their goals. Sound signal, in other words, provides a direct connection between the inner world and reality.

One of the leading scientists in psychology E.P. According to Ilyin, emotional intelligence in its content is the cause of a complex intellectual operation, which ultimately ends with the function of emotional intelligence. T. Piboga, using psychological, physiological, and pathological differences in the analysis of emotional response, assumes the existence of an affective type of the patient. That is, affective speech is a psychological response to our emotional sphere.

Researcher T.I. Solodkova P. Solovey and J. Analyzing the "model of emotional intelligence" compiled by Meijeplap, he mentions the optimal set of human emotional intelligence abilities:

- ability to identify, evaluate, and express emotions;
- the ability to emotionally express and evoke feelings to increase the efficiency of thinking;
- ability to understand emotions and emotional cognition;
- consciously train emotions, control emotions;
- the ability to exceed the level of emotional and intellectual development.

According to the content of this classification, our basic emotional state is realized as a function of emotional memory. That is, the physiological process of reprogramming inherent in emotional memory largely contributes to the restoration of our emotional experience associated with the past. Some studies claim that it is unrealistic to link emotional intelligence to a person's level of intelligence. In science, emotional intelligence is not associated with factors such as education and status but is a unique psychological factor that shapes it. According to Alfred Adler, the result of the test is not only self-awareness and self-knowledge but also the creative part of the inner mind when hiring a person for a job or educational institution. Specific training in emotional intelligence is not an easy task. This song has a DJ again. Mape, P. It is appropriate to pay attention to the content of the model of emotional

intelligence developed by Nightingale. The inventive part of the model is summarized as follows:

- knowledge about emotions;
- managing emotions;
- ability to self-motivate and overcome social interactions, etc.

But after much searching, D. Goleman developed a more complete model that explains his emotional intelligence. According to this model, the highest level of emotional intelligence is characterized by the following set of abilities:

1. Self-awareness;
2. Possibility of self-submission of an application;
3. The ability to motivate yourself;
4. The ability to empathize;
5. Ability to have social skills.

This model differs from other models in which D. Goleman tried to pay a lot of attention to individuality and social virtues inherent in the individual. According to my research, emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to understand and manage other people's emotions. This episode emphasizes internal and personal intelligence. Although the two creative parts of the conversation group are explained separately by knowledge and skills, they are inextricably linked. This thought D.V. According to Lucin, it is incorrect to describe emotional intelligence only in terms of cognitive abilities since this ability is closely related to understanding emotions and managing emotions. Based on the above hypothesis, emotional intelligence is a secondary psychological trait that depends on cognitive abilities and personality traits.

In our opinion, emotional intelligence has a typical nature, and before understanding it, it is important to first determine the nature of individual psychological characteristics. For example, N. In his research, Hall classifies the following content aspect of emotional intelligence.

1. Emotional consciousness;
2. Understanding emotion;
3. Self-motivation;
4. Strong empathy;
5. Being able to recognize a stranger's human feelings.

Much of the content of the model is that emotional awareness is responsible not only for our feelings but also for our understanding of the feelings of others. Karpov attempts to analyze emotional intelligence based on "metacognitive" principles and describes it as a metauniversal phenomenon. Because emotional intelligence must be characterized by elements of the cognitive and behavioral domains. For example, K. In his model, Isapd states that the integral aspect of emotional intelligence and the negative aspect of emotional intelligence represent the sum of related abilities. However, this model does not take into account the categorization of emotional intelligence. That is, the iPod function does not fit into this category. In the context of my study, it is also possible to increase the likelihood of explaining emotional intelligence in terms of a social-psychological basis..

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